

Segmental Angular Momenta Analysis in Perturbed Human Walking for Stability of Lower Limb Exoskeleton

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Abstract- This paper presents preliminary results of segmental angular momenta analysis in human walking subjected to lateral pelvic perturbations. The results show that angular momenta of specific segments, right upper leg and right foot in the study, were mostly affected by the applied perturbations. This finding will be further utilized to develop a perturbation detection method for monitoring stability while lower limb exoskeleton-supported walking.

Keywords—Angular momentum; walking; perturbation

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently angular momentum has been in the spotlight as it facilitates to not only describe the logic behind human walking dynamics but also control postural balance of bipedal robots [1]. Up to date, Centroidal Angular Momentum (CAM), referring to angular momentum at the center of mass, has been mainly examined and few studies on Segmental Angular Momenta (SAM) have been presented. Moreover, few results dealing with perturbed walking have been demonstrated [2]. In this paper, we present the results of SAM analysis in human walking subjected to lateral pelvic perturbations using a statistical approach. The benefit of the use of SAM over CAM is to require less sensor sets as well as computing power in monitoring gait stability.

II. METHOD

Kinematic data of 7 body segments shown in TABLE I of a healthy subject were measured while straight walking on a customized treadmill. Total forty lateral perturbations, applied at the pelvis timed immediately after right toe off, were randomly generated while walking. Details of the experimental setup as well as recording data are found in [3]. Using the recorded data, the mean of normalized SAM for forty unperturbed gait cycles were calculated followed by the calculation of normalized SAM for forty perturbed gait cycles. Then, the root mean square errors (RMSE) of SAM were computed by

$$RMSE_i = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^N |X_{pi,k}^j - X_{up,k}^j|^2}{N}} \quad (1)$$

where $X_{pi,k}^j$ denotes each SAM in j direction (X, Y and Z) at the k -th sampling instance under the i -th perturbation ($i=1, \dots, 40$), $X_{up,k}^j$ the mean of each SAM in j direction at the k -th sampling instance in the unperturbed walking, and N total number of the samples in each gait cycle. The RMSE of the selected forty unperturbed gait cycles were also calculated for One-way ANOVA test.

III. RESULTS

TABLE I shows the results of statistical analysis. While angular momenta of most segments are significantly affected by the perturbations, the Y directional angular momenta of RLL and RF have the smallest p-values. This finding can be

explained by the onset timing of the perturbations when the right leg is in swing phase, resulting in large reaction of the right leg in order to compensate the perturbations.

TABLE I. STATISTICAL TEST OF PERTURBATION INFLUENCE ON SEGMENTAL ANGULAR MOMENTA

Segment	Axis	Walking (Mean±SD of RMSE)		p-value
		Unperturbed	Perturbed	
HAT (Head, arms, trunk)	X	0.0120540±0.0023812	0.0151486±0.0049578	0.0006384
	Y	0.0018644±0.0003800	0.0028709±0.0015683	0.0001733
	Z	0.0016073±0.0005640	0.0024886±0.0015604	0.0012114
Right Upper Leg (RUL)	X	0.0042814±0.0013650	0.0055120±0.0019071	0.0013770
	Y	0.0017425±0.0004128	0.0022143±0.0006835	0.0003525
	Z	0.0021267±0.0006022	0.0028894±0.0012919	0.0011202
Left Upper Leg (LUL)	X	0.0042116±0.0012569	0.0057718±0.0020008	0.0000766
	Y	0.0018680±0.0003952	0.0023852±0.0006670	0.0000657
	Z	0.0021008±0.0005391	0.0028943±0.0009402	0.0000143
Right Lower Leg (RLL)	X	0.0071349±0.0027760	0.0091351±0.0046793	0.0226679
	Y	0.0024096±0.0006165	0.0041460±0.0019047	0.0000005
	Z	0.0007835±0.0002610	0.0014964±0.0008552	0.0000029
Left Lower Leg (LLL)	X	0.0068963±0.0022631	0.0090712±0.0039148	0.0032004
	Y	0.0024966±0.0005610	0.0036327±0.0015113	0.0000274
	Z	0.0007735±0.0002206	0.0011153±0.0004377	0.0000327
Right Foot (RF)	X	0.0073686±0.0029385	0.0088448±0.0040765	0.0669503
	Y	0.0012984±0.0003587	0.0024710±0.0013623	0.0000012
	Z	0.0009166±0.0003180	0.0012591±0.0005496	0.0010274
Left Foot (LF)	X	0.0064888±0.0024140	0.0080098±0.0026979	0.0095519
	Y	0.0013240±0.0002862	0.0020032±0.0010577	0.0001889
	Z	0.0008578±0.0003161	0.0011210±0.0003939	0.0014752

X: medio-lateral direction, Y: anterior-posterior direction, and Z: vertical direction.

IV. CONCLUSION

We presented analysis results of segmental angular momenta while perturbed walking. The results reveal that specific segments are most dominantly affected by the applied perturbations. Further study will be to incorporate this finding into online perturbation detection that is useful to monitor stability while walking supported by a lower-limb exoskeleton.

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